

PECULIARITIES OF TOURIST DESTINATION IN UZBEKISTAN CROSSING THROUGH THE GREAT SILK ROAD

Gulnoza Ilkhomova

Master of science on Tourism Leader specialist of Tourism Development Institute Tashkent,
Republic of Uzbekistan

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-4378-0772>

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Abstract. Current thesis discusses the Peculiarities of tourist destinations in Uzbekistan crossing through the Great Silk Road that allow to take a strong position in the international Travel services, competing in the world community. The global trends in the development of tourism services and the possibilities of Uzbekistan to integrate into upward trends are being studied. Ultimately, sustainable, and memorable tour experiences hinge on a holistic approach that cohesively merges the marquee destinations with diligent operations and a valued workforce were studied. Those able to master this merged production process will be optimally positioned to thrive in the competitive tourism industry landscape.

Keywords: silk road destination, Conceptual framework, Online Travel Agencies, Targeting, cultural legacy.

Annotatsiya. Joriy tezis ishi O‘zbekistonning Buyuk Ipak yo‘li orqali o‘tuvchi turistik yo‘nalishlarining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari ko‘rib chiqiladi, bu esa jahon hamjamiyatida raqobatbardosh bo‘lgan xalqaro sayyohlik xizmatlarida mustahkam o‘rin egallash imkonini beradi. Turizm xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning jahon tendensiyalari va O‘zbekistonning yuksalish tendensiyalariga integratsiyalashuv imkoniyatlari o‘rganilmoqda. Oxir oqibat, barqaror va esda qolarli ekskursiya tajribalari marvarid yo‘nalishlarini tirishqoq operatsiyalar va qadrli ishchi kuchi bilan birlashtiradigan yaxlit yondashuvga bog‘liq. Ushbu birlashtirilgan ishlab chiqarish jarayonini o‘zlashtira oladiganlar raqobatbardosh turizm sanoati landshaftida gullab-yashnash uchun eng maqbul joylashuvga ega bo‘ladilar.

Kalit so‘zlar: ipak yo‘li destinatsiyasi, kontseptual asos, onlayn sayohat agentliklari, nishonlash, madaniy meros.

Аннотация. Данная тезисная работа рассматривает особенности туристических направлений в Узбекистане, пересекающих по Великому Шелковому пути, которые позволяют занять прочную позицию в сфере международных туристических услуг, конкурируя в мировом сообществе. Изучаются мировые тенденции в развитии туристических услуг и возможности Узбекистана интегрироваться в восходящие тенденции. В конечном итоге, были изучены устойчивые и запоминающиеся туристические впечатления, основанные на целостном подходе, который сплоченно объединяет популярные направления с добросовестной работой и ценной рабочей силой. Те, кто сможет освоить этот объединенный производственный процесс, будут оптимально позиционированы для процветания в конкурентной среде туристической отрасли.

Ключевые слова: направление Шелкового пути, концептуальная структура, онлайн-турагентства, таргетинг, культурное наследие.

Introduction

Uzbekistan creates numerous opportunities for the Development and modernization of the Tourism sector for the sustainable development of the industry. Uzbekistan improves and develops regulatory framework as well as tourist services with International Standards. In developing Tourism Government, they aimed to put Policies. So, in the future, these should become the main areas for the Integrated development of the country as well as its infrastructure facilities. [1] Development in Tourism creates factors they are new jobs, diversification increasing incomes of regions, increasing the quality of life, increasing foreign exchange earnings, as well as attractiveness in the investment of the country. In 2016-2017 the annual growth rate of tourists increased from 8% to 33.7%. In 2018 the figure exceeded by almost 2 times. In 2019 foreign visitors came to Uzbekistan figure was 6,748.500. They questioned and studied the foreign tourist about their expectation and preferences. In the Global economy, tourism is found of the leading sector which is why in The Tourism Industry the places of Uzbekistan are particularly important for their modern culture. The improvement as well as the development of the conceptual framework for tourism sustainable development as well as international standards in tourist service.

Tourism sector

The region's history of being part of the Silk Road and its rich cultural heritage make it a compelling destination for tourists. However, geopolitical tensions, border disputes, and security concerns can also impact tourism flows. Cultural Heritage: Central Asia is home to diverse cultures, languages, and traditions, including those of Turkic, Persian, and Mongolian origins. The preservation and promotion of this cultural heritage play a crucial role in tourism development. Efforts to showcase historical sites, traditional crafts, music, and cuisine can attract cultural tourists seeking authentic experiences. Infrastructure and Accessibility: Developing tourism infrastructure, including transportation networks, accommodation options, and tourist facilities, is essential for attracting visitors. Improving air and road connectivity within the region and enhancing border crossings can facilitate tourism growth. Additionally, investing in hospitality services and promoting sustainable tourism practices are key considerations. Marketing and Promotion: Effective marketing and promotion strategies are vital for raising awareness of Central Asia as a tourism destination. Collaborative marketing campaigns among Central Asian countries or with neighboring regions can leverage shared cultural ties and attractions. Consideration of aspects of the development of the foundations of international hospitality in Uzbekistan in our culture, as well as integration processes and modern trends in international hospitality and their economic development in the country is becoming one of the leading areas. [6] Also, the potential and problems of integration, the development of the hotel business in the tourism market is a highly profitable area to ensure the high-quality development of international tourism. International activities with the development of the use of artificial intelligence to increase its efficiency and maintain relevance, as well as create favorable conditions for recreation and entertainment in the service sector for tourists arriving in Uzbekistan and for local tourists in the country. Socio-economic potential and promotion of the tourism brand in the international market, which are the main criteria for developing recommendations and considering the unique cultural heritage and infrastructure, comfortable recreation, factors such as political stability, and the safety of tourists becomes the highest priority issue in the dynamics of development. The strategy of Tourism Development has main sectors in the Transportation field as Railway, Airport, and Airline services which generate Destination Tourism products in well-known cities as Bukhara, Samarkand, and Khiva Old City. As well as dividing according to tourist purposes as medical, Business (MICE –

Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, Exhibitions) or recreation activities. This figure describes beneficial cooperation between the main sectors of Uzbekistan with OTA (Online Travel Agencies) as Booking, Airbnb, Expedia, Hostelworld, Vrbo, RatwHawk, or VocationReneter. Which actively uses artificial intelligence (AI) to select more optimal options for travelers. Destination management research includes not only geographical location but also digital location of accommodation and environmental standards.

Cultural legacy

Central Asian art encompasses a rich and diverse cultural heritage that reflects the region's history, traditions, and influences from various civilizations. Here are some key aspects of Central Asian Traditional Crafts which are renowned for their traditional crafts, including carpet weaving, embroidery, ceramics, metalwork, woodworking, and textile production. Each Central Asian country has its distinct styles and techniques, often passed down through generations within artisan families or communities. Islamic art has had a significant influence on Central Asian art, particularly in architecture, calligraphy, and decorative arts. The region is home to stunning examples of Islamic architecture, such as mosques, madrasas, mausoleums, and minarets adorned with intricate geometric patterns, arabesques, and floral motifs and it should be mentioned that, that the Silk Road influenced Central Asia's position along the historic Silk Road facilitated cultural exchanges between East and West, leading to the cross-pollination of artistic styles and ideas. The region served as a hub for the trade of silk, spices, ceramics, and other luxury goods, influencing art and craftsmanship across Eurasia. Historical aspects of the nomadic cultures of Central Asia have produced distinctive forms of art and material culture, characterized by portable and practical designs suited to a nomadic lifestyle. Nomadic art often features motifs inspired by nature, animals, and the celestial realm, as well as techniques like felt making, leatherwork, and ornamentation of textiles and horse trappings. Central Asian folk art encompasses a wide range of traditional expressions, including music, dance, storytelling, oral poetry, and ritual practices. Cultural Fusion art reflects the region's multicultural heritage, incorporating influences from Turkic, Persian, Arabic, Chinese, Russian, and other cultural traditions. This cultural fusion is evident in the synthesis of artistic styles, motifs, and techniques found in architecture, decorative arts, and visual culture throughout the region. The Museums and Cultural Institutions in Central Asia are home to a wealth of museums, galleries, and cultural institutions dedicated to preserving and showcasing the region's artistic heritage. These institutions play a vital role in promoting cultural exchange, education, and appreciation of Central Asian art both locally and internationally. [2] Overall, Central Asian art is characterized by its diversity, beauty, and historical significance, reflecting the region's rich tapestry of cultures, traditions, and artistic innovations shaped by centuries of interaction and exchange. Accordingly, in-depth knowledge of art or history impresses targeted tourists. Therefore, comprehensive research on traditional handicrafts is displayed in this atlas.

Targeting is a defining focus of the marketing research process and the core of cultural heritage attractions, so the right approach to groups of people with similar interests will have a progressive approach to increasing tourists. Advertising will always help with this, but advertising or promotion wherever possible is not the appropriate solution and therefore it is necessary to focus on narrower platforms, for example, advertising of cultural products can be distributed precisely in circles where it is required, as in the domain of archaeologists, artists, photographers, animators, historians, archivists, bibliographies, restorer, source specialists, ethnographers, fashion designer, interior designers, filmmakers, because cultural values are always and at all times different and

attract great interest from people who are associated with the history and art. Besides, from travelling everyone can obtain great and positive emotions that will create unforgettable inspiration. [4] This scheme was created following a book by Uzbekistan authors with the International Institute for Central Asian Studies example of Uzbekistan the Value I.

Figure 1 The Great Silk Road. Source: "Silk Road". Encyclopedia Britannica

Today, the legacy of the Silk Road continues to shape the cultural and economic landscape of the region.

Crossroads of Silk Road destinations

The central part of the village is located on the left bank. The site stands on a rectangular hill 15 meters high. The central part of the city (shahristan) was located on an area of 240x210 meters and was surrounded by two walls 17 and 25 km long. During the excavations, numerous ceramic, bronze and iron finds were discovered, as well as about 5,000 copper coins from the Karakhanid period.

Afghanistan	Kazakhstan	Kyrgyzstan	Tajikistan	Turkmenistan	Uzbekistan
Minaret and Archaeological Remains of Jam	Silk Roads: the Routes Network of Chang'an-Tianshan Corridor	Sulaiman-Too Sacred Mountain	Proto-urban Site of Sarazm	State Historical and Cultural Park “Ancient Merv”	Itchan Kala
Cultural Landscape and Archaeological Remains of the Bamiyan Valley	Petroglyphs of the Archaeological Landscape of Tanbaly	Silk Roads: the Routes Network of Chang'an-Tianshan Corridor	Tajik National Park (Mountains of the Pamirs)	Kunya-Urgench	Samarkand – Crossroad of Cultures

	Mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi	Western Tien-Shan	Silk Roads: Zarafshan-Karakum Corridor	Parthian Fortresses of Nisa	Western Tien-Shan	
	Saryarka – Steppe and Lakes of Northern Kazakhstan		Tugay forests of the Tigrovaya Balka Nature Reserve	Silk Roads: Zarafshan-Karakum Corridor	Cold Winter Deserts of Turan	
	Cold Winter Deserts of Turan				Cold Winter Deserts of Turan	Silk Roads: Zarafshan-Karakum Corridor
	Western Tien-Shan					Historic Centre of Shakhrisyabz
						Historic Centre of Bukhara

Figure 2 Heritage list among Central Asian countries

Source: UNESCO World Heritage list

Most of the identified buildings are located along the river. The Republic of Kazakhstan played a significant role as one of the main points of the Great Silk Road with regular trade diplomatic points around the steppes among foreign merchants, including large trade turnover of the continents. [3] The Silk Road was a network of trade routes that facilitated the exchange of goods, ideas, and culture between different civilizations, including China, India, Persia, and Rome nowadays tourism along the Silk Road offers visitors a unique opportunity to explore the rich history, diverse cultures, and stunning landscapes of the region. Silk Road destination tourism has become increasingly popular in recent years, attracting travelers from around the world. The promotion of sustainable tourism practices can support the preservation of the region's cultural and natural heritage for future generations. In conclusion, Silk Road destination tourism offers a unique opportunity to explore the historical and cultural significance of the ancient trade route. The development of sustainable tourism practices can support economic growth and environmental conservation, promoting the preservation of the region's cultural and natural heritage.

Conclusion

The findings revealed that Uzbekistan among Silk Road destinations possesses a rich tapestry of heritage sites reflecting its ancient history along the Silk Road trade routes. From the well-preserved medieval cities like Khiva and Bukhara to the petroglyphs at the Tamgaly site, these countries boast a remarkable collection of cultural heritage properties. [5] However, the region also faces significant challenges in areas like sustainable tourism management, conservation efforts, and community engagement. Moving forward, continuing to inscribe deserving Central Asian sites on the World Heritage List will be vital for safeguarding this legacy. At the same time, more comprehensive heritage policies, increased funding, public awareness

campaigns, and international cooperation will be needed. Green building techniques utilizing local, sustainable materials should also be incentivized. Investments in protecting natural assets like national parks, wildlife reserves, and bodies of water through conservation efforts will safeguard the resources drawing ecotourists. [7] Revenue generated could be directed into environmental management and regeneration projects. Supporting eco-entrepreneurship opportunities in sectors like sustainable agriculture, handicrafts, and ecotourism services will generate green jobs and inculcate circular economic models. Prioritizing partnerships with companies demonstrating environmental and social responsibility will foster this ecosystem. Embedding these priorities from the outset will ensure the long-term viability and global competitiveness of the region's tourism offerings.

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